

Imperative of Funding the Police: Brutality of Citizens in Nigerian Society Discourse

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Abstract:- Police violence against citizens is a common knowledge in Nigeria and it is on this basis that the prevalent public perception for the members of the force has generally been that of consternation, hatred and calumny. The police are regarded as violent extortionists, torturers, unfriendly, thieves, murderers, retched, undesirable, nuisance and the likes. The study focused on the need for adequate funding as a means of cubing the inimical behaviour observed among the force members. The article argues that to arm poorly remunerated Nigerian police men and women and send them to work among the public is to indirectly empower aggressively hungry men and women to extract money from the same people they are expected to protect. On this basis, it is recommended that the police trust fund law and the salary increment pronounced by the president since 2018 be implemented speedily with strict supervision.

Keywords:- police funding, police brutality, security, general strain, end SARS.

I. INTRODUCTION

Police brutality is a longstanding experience in the Nigerian social milieu which has triggered not just hatred but disdain for the men of the force such that not even the cliché “police is your friend has been able to change” anything about it. This may provide an explanation for why it is common to hear people boast of having their relatives in the Nigerian Army, Navy, Air Force and Customs but very few Nigerians would associate themselves with the Nigerian police force. Today, as the police is known, rightly or wrongly so, it is associated with so much contradictions against what it is supposed to represent. These contradictions are partly manifested in their belligerent behaviour towards the civil population which they were to protect in the first place in acts like, insults, assaults, battery, extrajudicial killing, unlawful arrest, detention, extortion and abetment of armed robbery groups in their nefarious endeavours against poor citizens.

For instance, the recent protest all over the nation tagged end SARS (Special Anti-Robbery Squad) is a vivid pointer to police brutality for which ill funding amidst others precursors was implicated as one of the causes when they advocated for better pay and equipping of police officers as major consideration in achieving reformed police. This conjectural influence of poor funding on police incivility is in

line with the common theories that lack or poverty fuels aggression (Evans & Cassells 2014), and for the Nigerian Police application of undue force or threat has been a means of extracting the resources which the government has failed to make available to them from the citizens.

Today, most Nigerians would do all they can to avoid police case for fear of exploitation and aggression even when they have unduly suffered wrong from miscreants. More Nigerians have devised means of coping with crime victimization, control or even prevention without involving the police- Little wonder why the official crime statistics are utterly unreliable. Myriad of reasons in connection with under-funding have been advanced for these prevalent inimical manifestations associated with the men of the force. Some of which are poor screening, training and retraining, poor remuneration and working environment (Alemika & Chukwuma 2000; Igbo 2007; Ayitogo 2020). Odotola (2020) laid bare the paltriness of police funding when he presented NPF’s allocation since 2018 as thus: ₦324.2 billion in 2018, ₦366.13 billion in 2019, ₦403.45 billion in 2020 and a proposed ₦447.6 billion in 2021. In additions, Ojukwu (2016) in his six years (2009-2014) analysis of police funding observed that despite the littleness of the police allocation, not up to 50 % have ever been released- in 2013 for instance, the released fund was as low as 5% of the originally proposed capital budgetary allocation. The allocated amounts are almost nothing compared to that which the United State Police and other Nigerian based law enforcement agencies enjoy.

According to U. S. Census of Governments, state and local governments spent \$115 billion on police in 2017 (the latest year for which comprehensive data are available). Across the US, police spending accounted for roughly \$1 of every \$10 spent by counties, municipalities, and townships and \$1 of every \$100 spent by the states. Police funding in the U. S. is reckoned to be the second largest category of local government spending after education. On the average, the United States spends \$340 per person per year for public policing, for a total of \$193 billion in spending in 2017. Police spending accounts for 9.2% of all local government spending. This works out to \$192,940 per police officer, including part-time employees. The police in the US receive funding from a variety of revenue streams, including local public funds, federal grants, fines and fees forfeitures and private donations (USA Facts, 2020; Auxier, 2020). This may explain why they are generally more civil to the citizens

when compared to Nigerian Police. Also, placing the financial allotment of the police side by side that of other law enforcement agencies in the country further calls for trepidation. For instance, ₦127b was allocated to the National Assembly of negligible number of persons in the 2021 appropriation bill. Also, over ₦800b was allotted to the Nigerian army which has fewer operations than the police.

From the foregoing, inadequate funding which has extremely undermined the training, logistics, recruitment, equipping and staff welfare could be indicted for police brutality as a hungry man is an angry man. It is against this backdrop that the issues raised here has been flagged up for this study with the intention of making recommendations for progressive change in the Nigerian police system.

II. THE PROBLEMATIQUE

The low funding of the Nigeria Police Force has been at the foundation of their brutality in Nigeria and on citizens. As the least funded law enforcement agency with much expectation from the government and citizen, the men of the force are pushed to the streets and appears to be left with no choice than to wrongfully and forcefully extract money from innocent Nigerians by means of false allegations, threats, arrest and torture. They are seen on the road mounting check points- some illegal, not necessarily for security purposes but for financial exploitation (*rodger, egunje or bushclearing*) of commercial vehicle drivers and riders. Anyone who fails to pay is either delayed as a way of punishment or dragged to the station on the basis of some made-up allegations to justify the arrest. In a bid to make much illegal collections from the road users, they even overlap the functions of the Vehicle Inspection Officers (VIOs) and the Road Safety personnel. Even though it is boldly written at the reception of the station that bail is free, yet the police charge for it. They raid some areas and make indiscriminate arrest at times just to cough out bail from innocent citizens.

The poor funding of the Force has made it impossible for police training and retraining, the payment of attractive salaries to commensurate with the degree of risk and hazard their work entail. Also, the non-compensation for the family member of men of the force who lose their lives on the course of duty, abysmal living condition of the men etc. culminates and reflects in the frustration the men of the force vent on citizens all over the nation. In fact, this their low socio-economic status appears to keep them subservient to the whims and caprices of corrupt politicians who also engage them unethically during election thereby worsening their already denigrated image. It is to this end that the paper was written to address the issues of Inadequate funding and police brutality in Nigeria with the aim of proffering possible panacea for positive change.

III. PALTRINESS OF NIGERIA POLICE FORCE MEN AND WOMEN'S PAY

There has been much clamor about the aggression of Nigerian police but the area of poor police funding arguably has not received equivalent attention. What should Citizens expect when police men have to pay for their own guns, uniforms, fuel the patrol vehicle with their own money, pay for their own health care, amidst other legitimate necessary expenditure for the dependent members of their household with a meagre salary?

Nigeria police is the least paid among corresponding security agencies in Nigeria and tens of thousands of them receive some of the poorest pay in the West African sub-region, a factor pundits argue encourages extortion and abuse of power. Across Nigeria, wretched police officers live in squalid neighborhood within and outside the barrack and go to work with broken down vehicles some from uncompleted buildings and garages. A Police recruit who is the lowest paid receives a consolidated annual salary of ₦108, 233.00 and a monthly consolidated salary of ₦9,019.42. But when ₦676.46 is deducted as pension, the recruit goes home with ₦8,342.96. Where as an equivalent of a police recruit in Ghana receives ₦77,000, besides a better training and welfare package than their Nigerian counterparts (Aytogo, 2020; Insine 2014). Little wonder why they tend to be more civil than their counterparts in Nigeria.

A comprehensive examination of the welfare packages of the law enforcement agencies further shows that the Police force suffer relative deprivation amongst their security counterparts in the country. For instance, while the IG of police earns a monthly pay of ₦711,498, the Director-General of State Security Service (SSS) earns ₦1,336 million per month and the Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC) Chairman gets about ₦1.5 million monthly. This treatment appears to lack justification with a staff strength of nearly 400,000, the Nigeria police is the principal law enforcement and lead security agency in the country consisting of 36 state commands grouped into 12 zones and seven administrative organs including special units such as the disbanded SARS.

Aytogo, (2020) observed that the Consolidated Police Salary Structure (CONPOSS) released in March 2011 and obtained by premium time which appears to be the only detailed document on salaries of the police in the public domain police earnings indicates that a Sergeant Major who is the 12th in rank and the most senior of the rank and file junior officers and a highest ranked of the non commissioned officers gets nothing appealing also. A Sergeant Major on Grade 06 (step 10) gets ₦62,204.88 monthly and Sergeant Major on same grade level but on step 1 gets ₦55,144.81. Among the Commissioned officers, a Cadet Inspector on Grade 07 (step 10) receives about ₦87,135.10 per month while a Cadet Inspector on same grade level but on step 1 is paid ₦73,231.51. The inspector general of Police who is the highest in rank and an appointee of the president who could be fired at any time is paid a monthly salary an annual salary of ₦8,537,980. For a more comprehensive

view, the below table 1 has been adopted to show the salary structure of men of the Nigeria Police force by rank.

S/NO	Ranks	Monthly Salary	Annual Salary
1	Police Recruit	N9,019.42	108,233
2a	Police Constable Grade level 03	N43,293.83	N519,525.60
B	Police Constable Grade Level 10	N51,113.59	N613,363.08
3a	Police Corporal on Grade Level 04 (1)	N44,715.53	N536,586.36
B	Police Corporal on Grade Level 04 (10)	N51,113.49	N613,363.08
4a	Police Sergeant on Grade Level 05 (1)	N48,540.88	582,490.56
B	Police Sergeant on Grade Level 05 (10)	N55,973.84	N671,686.08
5a	Sergeant Major on Grade Level 06 (1)	N55,144.81	N661,737.72
B	Sergeant Major on Grade Level 06 (10)	N62,204.88	N746,458.56
6a	Cadet Inspector on Grade Level 07 (1)	N73,231.51	N878,778.12
B	Cadet Inspector on Grade Level 07 (10)	N87,135.70	N1,045,628.40
7a	Assistant Superintendent of Police Grade Level 08 (1)	N127,604.68	N1,531,256.16
B	Assistant Superintendent of Police Grade Level 08 (10)	N144,152.07	N1,729,824.84
8a	Assistant Superintendent of Police Grade Level 09 (01)	N136,616.06	N1,639,392.72
B	Assistant Superintendent of Police Grade Level 09 (10)	N156,318.39	N1,875,820.68
9a	Deputy Superintendent of Police on Grade Level 10 (1)	N148,733.29	N1,784,799.48
B	Deputy Superintendent of Police on Grade Level 10 (10)	N170,399.69	N2,044,796.28
10a	Superintendent of Police on Level 11 (1)	N161,478.29	N1,937,739.49
B	Superintendent of Police on Level 11 (10)	N187,616	N2,251,400.28
11a	Chief Superintendent of Police on Grade Level 12 (1)	N172,089.06	N2,065,068.72
B	Chief Superintendent of Police on Grade Level 12 (08)	N199,723.96	N2,396,687.52
12a	Assistant Commissioner of Police on Grade Level 13 (1)	N183,185.73	N2,198,228.76
B	Assistant Commissioner of Police on Grade Level 13 (1)	N212,938.96	N2,555,257.92
13a	Deputy Commissioner of Police on Grade Level 14 (1)	N242,715.65	N2,912,587.80
B	Deputy Commissioner of Police on Grade Level 14 (1)	N278,852.79	N3,346,233.48
14a	Commissioner of Police on Grade Level 15 (1)	N266,777.79	N3,201,333.48
B	Commissioner for Police on Grade Level 15 (06)	N302,970.47	N3,635,645.64
15	Assistant Inspector General of Police	N499,751.87	N5,997,022.44
16	Deputy Inspector General of Police	N546,572.73	N6,558,872.76
17	Inspector General of Police	N711,498.00	N8,537,976

Table 1: Salary structure of the men and women of Nigeria Police force by their ranks

Source: mysalary scale(2017) and the Nigerian Finder (nd).

IV. THE REALITY OF POLICE BRUTALITY IN NIGERIA

To state that the police has been excessively hostile to the public is to state the obvious as an average Nigerian will concur to this. The men and the women of the Force are almost symbolic of evil in the minds and conversation of several citizens of Nigeria. This perception sustained from the days of colonialism when the force was first instituted

remains till date. The profession arguably is nothing to pride in as most parents will discourage their wards from joining particularly as non-commissioned members who are actually the face of the police the general public get to interface with. To further portray the extent of police brutality, the table below adopted from a study by Alemika and Chukwuma (2000) will help amplify the argument:

S/NO	Nature of behavior	Yes	No
1	Respondents' experience		
A	Ever abused by Nigeria police	41.4 (230)	58.6 (326)
B	Ever slapped	20.(101)	80.0 (404)
C	Ever kicked	13.5 (72)	86.5 (460)
D	Ever beaten	14.8 (79)	85.2 (455)
E	Ever injured by police	10.6 (56)	89.4 (472)
F	Police ever pointed gun at you	22.5 (121)	77.5 (416)
G	Police ever threatened to shoot you	21.3 (114)	78.7 (421)
2	Respondent ever observe or witness:		
A	police abusing a citizen or suspect	79.5 (458)	20.5 (118)
B	police slapping a citizen or suspect	72.1 (411)	27.9 (159)
C	police kicking a citizen or suspect	69.0 (394)	31.0 (177)
D	police beating a citizen or suspect	73.2 (424)	26.8 (155)

E	police inflicting injury on a citizen or suspect	51.9 (287)	48.1 (266)
F	police pointing a gun at a citizen or suspect	63.3 (356)	36.7 (206)
G	police shooting a citizen or suspect	27.5 (144)	72.5 (380)
H	police receiving bribe	82.5 (494)	17.5 (105)
3	Ever observed police helping a citizen	59.1 (328)	40.9 (227)

Table 2: Experience and Observation of Police Brutality

Source: Adapted from Alemika and Chukwuma (2000)

Table 2 show that a number of citizens who have experienced police belligerence is far lesser than those who have witnessed it. The table indicates that 41 percent (230) persons among the respondents have been verbally abused by the personnel of the force. 101 persons amongst the 505 sampled have received a slap from a member of Nigeria Police, 13.5 percent (72) has been kicked, 14.8 percent (79) have been beaten, 10.6 percent (56) claimed to have been injured, 22.5 percent (121) have had police point a gun at them while 21.3 percent (114) have been threatened to be shot by a member of the force.

Responses for those who have merely witnessed police brutality show that 79.5 (458) percent of respondents have seen a member of the force abusing a citizen or suspect; 72.1 percent (411) have observed a policeman slapping a citizen or a suspect, 69 percent (394) have seen a citizen or suspected being kicked, 73.2 percent (424) have seen a citizen or suspect being beaten, 51.9 percent (287) have seen a citizen or suspect being injured, 63.3 percent (356) have seen a gun being pointed at a citizen or suspect, 27.5 percent (144) have seen the police shot at a citizen or suspect 82.5 percent (494) have seen an officer collecting bribe and only 59.1 percent (328) have seen an officer helping a citizen.

Treatment	Yes	No
Abused or insulted when arrest	80.3 (155)	19.7 (38)
Beaten or slapped	81.0 (158)	19.0 (37)
Threatened with weapons	73.2 (142)	26.8 (52)
Tortured in police cell	77.5 (148)	22.5 (43)
Denied water and food in the police cell	56.3 (71)	43.2 (54)
Denied contacts with relations and lawyer	56.8 (76)	43.7 (55)
Burnt with hot objects	39.7 (48)	60.3 (73)
Shocked with electric current	33.3 (40)	66.7 (80)
Pricked with needle or sharp	50.8 (62)	49.2 (60)

Table 3: Inmates treatment by Nigeria police

Source: Adapted from Alemika and Chukwuma (2000)

Table 3 shows the Nigeria Police’s treatment of inmates who are merely accused and yet to receive a court sentence. 80.3 Percent (155) of them have been abused or insulted when arrested, 81.0 percent (158) have been beaten or slapped, 73.2 percent (142) have been threatened with weapons, 77.5 (148) have been tortured in police cell, 56.3 percent (71) have been denied water and food in cell, 56.8 (76) have been denied contact with relations and lawyer, 39.7 percent (48) have been burnt with hot objects, 33.3 percent (48) have been shocked with electric current and 50.8 percent (62) have been pricked with needle or sharp object.

experienced and witnessed. It could also be suggested that the number of citizens who have heard about the Force’s hostility towards citizens will far outweigh the number of those who have both witnesses and experienced same put together.

In a similar study conducted by the department of Sociology/Anthropology, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka in 2008 substantiated the above study by Elemika and Chukwuma. According to the findings of the study, a significant number of citizens perceive the members of the police force as maltreating, harsh, abusive, abusers of power and excessively forceful (Ugwoke 2015). The table below expresses the position of respondents in specifics.

The above analysis clearly indicates various dimensions of police brutality Nigerians have both

Responses	Strongly Agree		Agree		Uncertain		Disagree		Strongly disagree	
	Frequen cy	Percen tage	Freque ncy	Percen tage	Freque ncy	Percen tage	Freque ncy	percenta ge	Freque ncy	Percenta ge
Threaten Citizen with a gun/weapon	118	12.7%	240	25.8%	122	13.1%	177	19.0%	274	29.4%
Harass suspects while being arrested	330	35.35 %	269	28.9%	107	11.5%	121	13.0%	103	11.1%
Maltreat suspects while in arrested	285	31.1%	264	28.8%	148	16.1%	126	13.7%	94	10.3%

Abuse of power	310	33.6%	256	27.8%	131	14.2%	122	13.2%	103	11.2%
Excessive use of force	295	29.5%	284	31.1%	118	12.9%	120	13.1%	96	10.5%

Table 4: Respondents' opinion on police Negative Behaviour in Anambra State

Source: Report of a Baseline Security Study conducted in Anambra State in 2008 by the Department of Sociology/Anthropology, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. as cited by Ugwoke(2015:115-116).

The findings in the above table 4 corroborates the fact that the members of the Nigeria Police Force have really been violent towards the public.

V. INADEQUATE EQUIPMENT AND POLICE BRUTALITY ON CITIZENS

Frustration has five dimension and layers first of which is Aggression. Others are withdrawal, Rationalization, compromise and fixation. Whenever frustration gets into the psychological core sphere and it becomes quite impossible to get rid of it rather it over powers everything else, the individual may be in an aggressive mode of frustration. Andalib, Darun, and Azizan, (2013). They further argued that frustration occurs when people's wishes, wants and desires get thwarted or interrupted. The feeling results from disparities between what people want and what we find available. For instance, when a police officer needs fuel for the patrol vehicle for a beat he has been directed to cover and he is technically told to generate the money. This automatically set the ground for the officers to search for individuals to victimize and hostility is likely to be the measures adopted. Also, if a team of police officers are sent with a patrol vehicle to intervene an ongoing criminal activity and the vehicle breaks down such that they experience a delay which affects their delivery on their assignment and attracted a disciplinary measure from their superior officers, the police officers tends towards violence on civilians by transferring aggression which they couldn't express to their superior.

Frustration arises due to various conflicts in the working atmosphere, threat and conflict also get overlapped with frustration in many cases. The police job is laden with so much risk which is amplified by the absence of working equipment like sophisticated guns, bullet proofs, sufficient and cooperating colleagues. The police men and women who have their families and life aspirations tend to see some of their assignments in the face of equipment scarcity as a set up for death and may not be willing to lay down their lives as sacrificial lambs for no tangible. With this condition it becomes virtually impossible to respond in a friendly manner to any citizen in distress who calls on them. Igbo (2007) and Okeshola (2008) cited in Ugwoke (2015) shear this believe when they independently identified shortage of equipment and shortage of staff as major problems of the Nigeria Police.

Citizens who lack this understanding of police handicap tend to develop enmity towards the police which they exhibit at any given opportunity. And chances for paroxysm of violent are high when a frustrated policeman on duty meets with a frustrated citizen who probably has suffered losses for what he perceives police ineffectiveness. In situation where a majority of the citizens are embittered

about police functions and begin to see them as foes, police officers may feel unsafe among the citizens and may adopt violence and intimidation as a mechanism of self-defense and ego protection. In line with this thoughts, Alemika and Chukwuma (2000), posited that the police have suffered much ills from the citizens. A number of them have been injured and others have lost their lives. They are usually targets during protest and riot. This recent #EndSARS protest is another lender of support to this fact as lots of police stations across the country were reportedly burnt down and some officers killed by hoodlums. Among other reports Adediran (2020) noted the killings, and injuries of a number of officers and counted over 10 stations set ablaze. The number of burnt police station were however reportedly increased to over 17 by OlumyiwaAdejobi the spokesperson of the police in Lagos (#End SARS:over 17 Police stations", 2020).

The chairman- Senate committee on police affairs HaliruJika in an interview with channels televisionon September 18th 2020 in a program tagged Sunrise Daily posited that the major problem of the Nigerian police is tied to funding which the police trust fund is meant to address. For him, the trust fund will cater for training and retraining, equipment acquisition and welfare of the officers. The Senator recounted further that while he was in the House of Representative as the chairman of the house committee on police affairs in 2015, he noticed that the running cost for a police division across the country was ₦35,000 which could not even cater for the required fuel quantity talk less of stationaries. He noted that the police overhead is barely ₦1.5b despite the myriad of operations going on. He compared this to the military where a singular operation is given ₦100b annually in the name of "fight against insurgency". He reiterated that the police have more operations but little funding and for him this is a major reason for which police men are brutal. He believes if funding were available the police officers would be not only being physically furnished but would also be intellectually equipped through training and retraining which will help them to be more civil. (Channels Television n.d.).

VI. IMPLICATION OF POOR SALARIES FOR POLICE BRUTALITY ON CITIZENS

Poverty over the years has been linked with aggression and other forms of street crimes, a poor policeman is more prone to violence than a rich police officer. An average Nigerian police officer cannot meet his/her basic needs given the reality of his take home pay visa vis the current economic situation. Mr Psayande's report of 2012 on police

reform suggested that this poor remuneration condition of service are factors affecting performance in the force. Nzube Akunne a Lagos based lawyer in the same vein agreed that poor remuneration is a factor to reckon with noting specifically that it breeds jealousy and envy against fellow Nigerians (Aytogo, 2020).

From a broader sense, family stress model assumes that family poverty which is a stress source makes it difficult for children to learn to control the behaviour problem of physical aggression (Mazza, Pingault, Booij, Boivin, Tremblay, Lambert, Zunzunegui, & Co[^] te, 2016). In other words, children from poor homes are most likely to express aggression. In the same vein, Evans and Cassells (2014) suggested that poverty may lead to responding harshly to those one is expected to be responsible to. From the light of these studies, it is surmised that the violence of the men of the force is a product of a double calamity that is, a combination of family background poverty's accumulated frustration and their job remuneration's frustration as it can be rightly argued that no one from a rich family would join the force as a rank and file officer. Put differently, the police violent officer who most citizens often interface with are non commissioned member who are likely to come from poor families and have not been able to learn to control their physical aggression. When the culture of violence that has been imbibed from childhood combines with the frustration arising from the meagre salaries earned in comparison to the work pressure they are subjected to, nothing less than hostility would be exhibited in the course of their relating with the members of the public.

Finally, if poverty has been linked to high predatory and survival crime rate in society as it is believed today, it is rational to argue therefore that the poverty of the policemen and women has in one way or the other pushed some of them into direct extortion of citizens or affiliation with robbery gangs, political thugs and corrupt politicians for financial rewards.

VII. GENERAL STRAIN THEORY

The general strain theory as propounded by Robert Agnew (1992) holds that there are three sources of strain. These sources include: (a) Failure to achieve positively valued goals. (b) Denial or removal of previously attained positive achievements (c) Exposure to negative noxious stimuli.

In line with paltry funding and police brutality, the first, support the perception that the police officers just like every other person who works have aspirations in life. They look forward to getting married, raising children, furthering their education, meeting their medical care needs, living in decent accommodations and living long. These are besides the expectations they have from their jobs. But in a circumstance where they are unable to achieve these desired goals, strain is generated and violence is unleashed on the citizens as either a means to meet those desired goals or as a means to ease off the stress. The officer maybe found making unlawful arrest and torturing the innocent citizens to extract money to meet his desired goals or as a way of getting back at the society for seemingly denying him the

opportunity to achieve his valued goals. Sometimes to meet their needs Ugwuoke (2015) posits that Nigeria Police force members go the extra mile of robbing accidents victims. Olumodeji and Ikoh(2014) posits that aspirations are loftier than expectations and as such, there exist more strain in disjunction between aspiration and achievements than in the disjunction between expectation and achievement.

The second source of strain which is the removal of positive achievement could support the thoughts that when police officers in the line of duty suffer injury as have been happening, or falls sick especially without compensation, they become more violent towards the general public. Also, if they lose their colleagues maybe to a gun duel with miscreants, they may become very unfriendly to anyone who though innocent but appears rough and may also answer aggressively when distress calls come to them from the victimized citizens.

The third source of strain provides an explanation for the harsh conditions the police men are exposed to and the strain it generates which in turn drives them into misconducts. For instance, the police officers are usually sent to cover beats without fuel, good vehicle, potable water. Most times they are exposed to the sun for hours at check points. These conditions around their work are generally offensive and serve as a trigger for unwelcoming behaviour towards citizens. Although the general strain theory may not explain corruption by top police officers who likely have better pay and access to a better working condition, its strengths suffices for the purpose of this study as has been demonstrated above. To this end, the theory is hereby adopted for the study.

VIII. RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION

Arming a hungry and frustrated police officer with gun as it in Nigeria today is more like empowering him for robbery. It is more like a huge setup which very few men of the force have been able to resist. Thus, the terror unleashed on the public is an offshoot of frustration which appears to have worked effectively for the members of the force in achieving some financial gains to make up for their poor funding. In this wise, it is recommended that the signed police trust fund be implemented with speed and properly supervised to eliminate its diversion into few pockets, the new salary scale for the members of the force be implemented with payment of all areas since 2008, free and decent housing and medical facilities be made available and accessible to the men of the force, funding for regular training and retraining of the personnel of the force and a worthwhile compensation be given to the relatives of all men of the force who lose their lives in the course of protecting citizens and the country at large.

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